

ISic2905

I.Sicily inscription 2905

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Piazza Armerina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Piazza Armerina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330707

1. [— — — — —]#⁷ [— — — — —]
2. [— — — — —]ETHΘ [— — — — —]
3. [— — — — —]KONTOΣ #⁵⁶ ΩΡ [— — — — —]
4. [— — — — —]στυ οργή (?) ΕΠ Ο [— — — — —]
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645298

EDCS 64900603

PHI 330707

Bibliography

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